

Validation of a Control Algorithm for the Efficient Charging of PCM energy storage tanks using an Emulation Platform

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ABSTRACT

As the world energy production shifts towards Renewable Energy Sources (RES), sophisticated control algorithms are required in order to efficiently extract, store, and consume power from RES. Addressing the difficulties that the intermittency of these sources is introducing to energy systems, can have a significant effect on reducing the cost of operation for RES energy systems and transform them from supplementary to base line solutions. When it comes to energy storage in the form of heat a proposed solution is Phase Change Materials (PCMs). To study the operation of RES systems, a variety of test rigs are proposed but their drawback is that the experiments are dependent on the environmental conditions in the testing area. Therefore, testing platforms that emulate the environmental conditions can prove useful as they enable the researchers to test scenarios regardless of the actual environmental conditions during tests. In this work a control algorithm for the efficient charging of PCM energy storage tanks by Solar Collectors (SCs) is validated. The controller runs in real time, reads temperature in various points of the system and controls the flow rate of the heat transfer fluid in order to achieve maximum power extraction from the solar collectors. The solar collectors are emulated using a mathematical model and a real-time emulation platform. The created model runs in real time and its output controls a mixing valve connected to a buffer tank, to emulate various operating conditions of the solar collectors. The same control algorithm is used again to charge the PCM tanks with the use of the solar collector emulation platform. By using this method, the operation of SCs under various conditions was emulated and the effect in the charging of the PCM tanks was studied. If the emulator platform proves to be able to closely emulate the SCs, it can be used to test the charging of PCM tanks, without actual solar collectors installed, thus the tests will not depend on actual environmental conditions (solar irradiance and temperature).

INTRODUCTION

PCM materials are gaining increased attention for solar thermal applications in general while latent heat storage for domestic hot water production is the most widely used application for PCMs [1,2]. Qiu et al reviewed the advantages and drawbacks of using PCMs for heat storage [3]. Furthermore, they have attributed the issue of decreased discharging efficiency of latent thermal energy storage tanks to the property of high thermal resistance that most PCM materials exhibit. To solve that problem researchers have investigated various enhancement methods which are also analyzed in their work.

Different control strategies can be employed for the efficient storage of solar heating energy. Flow control is the most widely used method with two alternatives: on-off control and proportional flow control. Araujo et al created a model for the study of both control strategies [4]. They came up with results proving that on-off control is more efficient for solar collectors with small effective area. On the contrary for solar collectors larger than about 2m² the proportional flow control strategy is more efficient as it increases solar fraction. The main function of a control system for solar thermal application beyond adjusting the flow rate of the Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF), is to protect the system from overheating. More specifically, latent thermal storage tanks suffer from overheating because PCMs degrade if heated beyond their fully charged limit. Furthermore, because PCMs self-ignite in relatively low temperatures (some have self-ignition temperature rating as low as 100°C) the importance of overheating prevention is significant [5]. Elias et al have implemented a hybrid predictive algorithm for overheating prevention of solar collectors [6]. Their application is targeting solar thermal plants but their control approach can be used for small solar collectors, too.

Because of the importance of control systems in solar heat storage applications and the additional control requirements that latent heat storage platforms introduce, controller for solar thermal applications became increasingly more complex. To study the behavior of these controllers, test rigs are needed. Peter et al have developed a such testing rig that interfaces the control signals directly and by generating the appropriate signals, a number of testing conditions are produced [7]. Then the output decisions of the controller under evaluation are measured and thus the behavior of the controller can be studied without the need of actual solar collector setup. In TESSe2b project [8] a solution targeting residential buildings has been developed that incorporates Thermal Energy Storage (TES) technology. The developed technology is based on solar collectors and highly efficient heat pumps as well as on thermal energy storage tanks for heating (HTES), cooling (CTES) and domestic hot water (DHW) production. It comprises solar thermal collectors, geothermal heat pump with vertical Borehole Heat Exchangers, the TESSe2b TES tanks with immersed heat exchangers and additional components as circulating pumps, control valves and the necessary sensors for control and monitoring. In this work results from the testing of the control system algorithms for charging and discharging of the HTES PCM tank [9] at laboratory level are presented and discussed. A similar approach as the one above is used in this work but instead of interfacing the control signals directly, a solar emulator is implemented which produces the same HTF conditions (temperature difference) that an actual solar collector would exhibit under the same environmental conditions (solar irradiance and ambient temperature).

EXPERIMENTAL RIG AND PROCEDURE

For the evaluation of the control algorithm a simple test case is considered, shown in Figure 1. Solar energy from an array of flat plate solar collectors is to be stored in a PCM storage tank at low storage temperatures. The stored energy is then directly supplied from the PCM tank to the heating end device that can be for example low-temperature fan-coil units or underfloor heating. The charging and discharging of the PCM storage tank is regulated by automatic controllers in order to efficiently store and use the solar energy at various conditions of solar availability and heat demand. The HTF is circulated through the PCM tank with the aid of a controllable variable speed circulation pump. In the real system to be implemented in the TESSe2b project [8], multiple PCM tanks will be installed depending on the heating demand of the house and a geothermal heat pump will operate in parallel in order to provide heating when solar energy is not available. There is also the option to store geothermal energy in the PCM tanks using the heat pump during a cheap electricity tariff and avoiding use of the heat pump during the expensive electricity tariff.

Figure 1 Solar collector – PCM tank test case

The properties of the developed PCM tank are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: PCM HTES tank information

Heat exchanger dimensions	238.1x950x600mm (Width-W, Length-L, Height-H)
Heat exchanger hydraulic connections	Charging: 12 circuits in parallel 6m long each Discharging: 12 circuits in parallel 6m long each
Inner plastic tank dimensions	300x1220x840mm (W, L, H) 10mm thickness
Outer metal tank dimensions	480x1400x1020mm (W, L, H) 1mm thickness
Insulation - density	Expanded polyurethane 80mm thickness, 40kg/m ³
Heat storage medium	A44 paraffin type phase change material
A44 PCM volume	260lt (liquid phase)
PCM melting point	317K
PCM freezing point	318.5K
Density (liquid phase)	0.754x10 ³ kg/m ³
Density (solid phase)	0.912x10 ³ kg/m ³
Specific heat (liquid phase)	1.8 kJ/kg K
Specific heat (solid phase)	2.4 kJ/kg K

For the discharging of the PCM tank, a variable speed circulator pump is also used to directly supply the load heating end devices. A mixing valve can be used at the output of the PCM tank to lower the flow temperature to the load if necessary. A number of temperature probes has been installed to measure the temperature of the HTF and the PCM inside the tank. The mass flow rate of the two circuits is measured with the flow meters installed and the solar radiation is measured by a weather station installed near the solar collectors. The type of sensors and actuators used as well as their position are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Sensors and actuators used on the testing rig

<i>Sensor name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Device type</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Position on the rig</i>
RTD1	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-150] °C	Solar collector outlet
RTD2	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-150] °C	PCM tank charging inlet
RTD3	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-150] °C	PCM tank charging outlet
RTD4	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-100] °C	PCM tank discharging inlet
RTD5	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-100] °C	PCM tank discharging outlet
RTD6	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-100] °C	Load inlet
RTD7	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-100] °C	PCM tank (PCM) temperature
RTD8	Temperature	Pt1000 / Class A / 4-wire	[0-100] °C	PCM tank (PCM) temperature
VFR_S	Flow meter	Turbine	[0-2] m ³ /hr	Charging loop
VFR_L	Flow meter	Turbine	[0-4] m ³ /hr	Discharging loop
Psolar	Circulator	Variable-speed / controlled by external PWM signal	-	Charging loop
Pload	Circulator	Variable-speed / controlled by external PWM signal	-	Discharging loop
AV1	VALVE	3-way control valve with controllable actuator	0-100% 35sec	Solar collector emulation system
AV2	VALVE	3-way control valve with controllable actuator	0-100% 35sec	Discharging loop

Using this setup, a set of charging and discharging experiments have been performed. For those experiments the control algorithm has been used to control the flow rate of the HTF in the charging loop (by adjusting the controllable circulator pump) so as to achieve maximum power extraction from the solar collectors. The control algorithm used is a digital proportional-integral controller with anti-windup element. The controller uses the solar collector outlet water temperature and PCM temperature as inputs and it generates the signal that controls the Circulation Pump (CP) speed in order to achieve temperature differential between the Solar collectors and PCM tank equal to the set-point. The set-point depends on the design characteristics of the solar collector and PCM tank and for this work, the value used, is considered as input parameter and not further studied. The controller is implemented in Matlab-Simulink® on a real-time dSpace MicroLabBox platform on which the analogue inputs from the sensors are read and output signal for circulator pump is generated as pulsed-modulated signal (PWM). The transfer function of the controller is:

$$e = \Delta T^* - (T_{SC} - T_{PCM}) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{y(s)}{e(s)} = \frac{K_p \cdot s + K_i}{s} \quad (2)$$

where: controller input, y : controller output, ΔT^* : temperature difference reference, T_{SC} : solar collector temperature, T_{PCM} : PCM tank temperature, K_p : controller proportional gain, K_i : controller integral gain, s : s transform variable. The block diagram of the controller in Simulink is presented on Figure 2. A simple user interface has been built in dSpace MicroLabBox in which all critical data for the experiments are shown in real time. Also, the user is able to directly control the output signals and change the set-points in real time. The user interface is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Block diagram of the solar charging controller

Figure 3 User interface

REAL-TIME EMULATION OF SOLAR COLLECTORS

In a real system, the HTF temperature at the outlet of a solar collector is not constant because a solar collector is a constant power source dependent on solar irradiation. More specifically, for a given type of solar collectors, the

outlet temperature depends on the following variables [9]: solar radiation, ambient air temperature, inlet temperature of the solar collectors (\approx outlet temperature of HTES), flow rate in the solar loop.

For the needs of the setup, a mathematical model of a solar collector was implemented in real-time on the dSpace[®] platform in order to dynamically calculate the outlet collector temperature during the experiments, depending on the above variables and typical parameters for flat-plate solar collectors with the same properties with those used in the experiments with real collectors. The calculated outlet collector temperature was given as a reference to a custom temperature controller designed for the analog mixing valve AV1. This temperature controller was developed in order to accurately control the temperature RTD2 at the inlet of the HTES that is the emulated outlet collector temperature, by dynamically varying the position of the valve to mix the outlet and return (inlet) of the buffer tank. Using this technique, the outlet of the mixing valve has the same temperature as calculated for the outlet of a solar collector and thus the buffer tank and mixing valve pair, emulate the behavior of a solar collector.

3.1 Solar collector model

The mathematical model of the solar collector that was implemented in real-time is presented here.

The thermal power output of the solar collector can be defined as the product of its conversion efficiency and intensity of solar irradiance.

$$\dot{Q}_{KN} = n_K * E * A_K \quad (3)$$

Where: n_K : Collector efficiency, Q_{KN} : Output thermal power of collector (W), E : Solar irradiance intensity (W/m²), A_K : Collector area (m²).

Depending on the type of solar collector and performance, the efficiency curve of a solar collector can be determined using three parameters provided by the solar collector manufacturer and the temperature difference between collector and ambient air [9]:

$$n_K = n_0 - \frac{\alpha_1 * (\theta_K - \theta_u) + (\theta_K - \theta_u)^2}{E} \quad (4)$$

Where: n_0 : Zero-loss collector efficiency, α_1 : Basic heat loss coefficient (W/m²K), θ_K : Mean collector temperature (K), θ_u : Ambient air temperature (K)

Thermal power of the solar collector is transferred to the HTF when circulation is active. The transferred power can be determined by the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{KN} = \left(n_0 - \frac{\alpha_1 * (\theta_K - \theta_u) + (\theta_K - \theta_u)^2}{E} \right) * E * A_K = \dot{m} * C_p * (\theta_{KO} - \theta_{KI}) \quad (5)$$

Where: θ_{KO} : Collector outlet temperature (K), θ_{KI} : Collector inlet temperature (K), \dot{m} : HTF mass flow rate (kg/s), C_p : heat capacity of HTF (J/kg K)

The mean collector temperature (θ_K) can be calculated as the mean of the outlet and inlet temperature:

$$\theta_K = \frac{\theta_{KO} + \theta_{KI}}{2} \quad (6)$$

Using the above equations, the outlet collector temperature can be calculated as a function of solar radiation, inlet collector temperature, flow rate and ambient air temperature. Typical performance parameters for different types of solar collectors are provided in Table 3. In the following tests the parameters for flat-plate, single glazing, selective absorbers were used for the real-time model with a total collector area of 25m². These parameters correspond to the solar collector system that will be installed in one of TESSe2b demo sites [8]. The modified hydraulic circuit with and the model solar collector emulation platform can be seen in Figures 4 & 5.

Table 3 Typical performance parameters of various solar collector types [10]

<i>Solar collector type</i>	<i>Zero loss collector efficiency, η_0</i>	<i>Basic heat loss coefficient α_1 (W/m²K)</i>
Unglazed absorber	0,91	12,0
Flat-plate, single-glazing, non-selective absorber	0,86	6,1
Flat-plate, single-glazing, selective absorber	0,81	3,8
Flat-plate, double-glazing, selective absorber	0,73	1,7
Vacuum tube	0,80	1,1

Figure 4 Modified hydraulic circuit with the emulation platform

Figure 5 Block diagram of the solar emulation algorithm in Simulink®

3.2 Experimental results of the real-time emulation of a solar collector model

Experiments were carried out on the test rig in order to test the performance of the solar collector emulation system. Typical results are shown in Figure 6. This experiment is used for the evaluation of the charging controller.

Figure 6 Real time emulation platform experimental results

For that, the PCM tank starts partially charged (mean PCM temperature of 42°C). At the start of the experiment a low constant flow is applied by the circulating pump and the controller for the AV2 mixing valve is inactive. During

this time the temperature RTD2 does not follow the emulated collector output temperature calculated by the collector model. At time 0.2 hours, the controller for the AV2 mixing valve is activated. After a brief transient, the temperature RTD2 follows the reference value of the collector outlet temperature with a very good accuracy. The valve position is dynamically adjusted by the controller to always follow the emulated collector outlet temperature that is dependent on the solar radiation, flow rate, collector inlet temperature and ambient air temperature. It must be noted that the flow rate in the solar loop does not depend on the position of the mixing valve because the pressure drop characteristic of the hydraulic loop with fully-open (hot buffer tank connected) and fully-closed (hot buffer tank by-passed) AV1 valve is very similar. Therefore, the flow rate depends only on the state of the circulating pump that is regulated by the PCM tank charge controller.

CHARGING TEST WITH EMULATED SOLAR COLLECTORS

Charging control strategies with the solar collectors include constant flow charging with on-off regulation of the flow rate and variable-flow charging which is the strategy used here. The results of the variable-flow charging tests are presented in the following section. Figure 7 shows the emulated solar radiation, the emulated collector outlet temperature, the measured inlet temperature of the HTES, the heat transfer rate with which the HTES is charged and the PCM temperatures measured inside HTES heat exchanger. Figure 8 shows the PCM temperatures measured with thermocouples at different locations inside the HTES. Figure 9 shows the reference and measured charging temperature and the charging flow rate.

The charging is started if the PCM temperature is below the maximum shut-off temperature for the respective HTES and if the collector outlet temperature is above the measured PCM temperature by a certain ΔT . In that case, the shut-off temperature for the A44 HTES was selected at 52 °C. The flow rate is continuously varied by the charge controller between a minimum value and a maximum value. The minimum flow used in the experiments was 4 l/min and the maximum flow rate was 20 l/min. The charge controller varies the flow rate in order to maintain the collector outlet at a certain temperature reference. This reference can be a constant value or calculated by other parameters. In the presented test the reference temperature was defined as the measured PCM temperature plus a constant ΔT . In other words, the controller varies the flow rate in order to keep the temperature difference between the collector outlet and the PCM constant. A single Pt1000 RTD sensor for the PCM temperature was used by the controller, RTD8 that was placed near the 'load'-side of the HTES and provides a good indication that most of the PCM has melted in the case of charging with solar collectors. A better indication of the PCM temperature can be seen in Figure 8. In this the values of several temperature sensors immersed in different positions in the PCM tank is shown. The optimal location of the PCM sensor(s) to accurately measure the average PCM temperature is yet to be defined. The reference temperature RTD8REF is shown in Figure 7. At the beginning of the test the reference temperature is set with a ΔT of 2 °C above the measured temperature RTD8. A proportional-integral controller is used to minimize the difference between solar collector outlet and the reference temperature by continuously adapting the flow rate. With this strategy, solar energy can be used to charge the HTES even at very low levels of solar radiation that is important during cloudy days with low direct solar radiation. The charging starts with minimum flow rate when the solar radiation is about 200 W/m². The flow rate is continuously increased up to about 15 lit/min at time 0.6 Hours when the solar radiation reaches 340 W/m² as shown in Figure 7. At this point the heat transfer rate between the 'solar collector' and the HTES is about 5 kW. Shortly after 0.6 Hours the ΔT is manually increased from 2 °C to 6 °C in order to observe the response of the controller. This relatively large difference between the reference and the measured RTD2 temperature is quickly compensated by the controller by automatically reducing the flow until the solar collector outlet temperature increases towards the reference temperature. As the solar radiation continues to increase the flow rate is increased by the controller until the maximum flow rate of 20 l/min is reached. After this point the reference temperature cannot be followed and the collector outlet temperature varies relatively proportional to the solar radiation. The charging is automatically stopped when the PCM temperature reaches the shut-off temperature of 52 °C.

Figure 7 Charging test experimental results

Figure 8 PCM temperature inside the HTES tank

Figure 9 Charging temperatures (top) & HTF mass flow rate (bottom)

The third graph of Figure 7 also shows the heat transfer rate delivered to the PCM tank by the solar collectors. The heat transfer rate depends on the solar radiation and the circulator pump speed set by the controller.

The temperature of the PCM is slowly increasing as it absorbs heat. The temperature sensor immersed in the PCM for the charging, shows higher temperature than the sensor immersed at the other side of the tank but this is due to bad thermal conductivity of the PCM. To solve this problem, a number of temperature elements can be immersed in the tank in a grid pattern and the average temperature of all sensors can be used as the mean PCM temperature (as shown in Figure 8). When the temperature of the PCM reaches the shut-off value, the charging procedure automatically stops. The PCM tank has reached full capacity and the controller completely stops the circulation pump. The temperature at the outlet of the solar collectors, quickly climbs at this point because heat is no longer absorbed by the PCM tank.

DISCHARGING AND SIMULTANEOUS CHARGING AND DISCHARGING TESTS

Further experiments were conducted to test the performance of the TESSe2b control system during discharging as well as during simultaneous charging and discharging of the HTES PCM tank. The control objective during discharging is to provide a constant temperature at the inlet of the load that is close to the nominal inlet temperature of the terminal heating unit. This reference temperature must be kept constant irrespective of the heating

load and thus irrespective of the total flow rate required by the heating load. Furthermore, the temperature must be maintained as far as possible close to the reference value during significant variations in the PCM temperature inside the HTES that can be a result of either charging or discharging actions. The results of the tests are provided in Figure 10 and Figure 11, in which the inlet temperature of the load is controlled by dynamically varying the opening of the three-way analog mixing valve shown as AV2.

Figure 10 Experimental results for PCM tank discharging.

Figure 11 Experimental results for PCM tank discharging.

The reference temperature used in the tests was 40 °C that is a typical nominal inlet temperature for low-temperature fan coils. The average flow rate in the load loop was about 8.33 l/min. Only at the beginning of the charging procedure, for a brief period of 2 minutes during which the valve opening is below 30% a higher flow rate of 10.8 l/min is observed due to the lower pressure drop in the piping when the HTES is by-passed. The inlet temperature to the HTES varies between 26 °C and 30 °C due to the characteristic of the buffer tank-equipped with a water chiller that was used to simulate the heating load. At the beginning of the charging procedure, the inlet temperature of the load (RTD6 in Figure 10) is quickly increased from 26 °C to 40 °C within 5 minutes and it is kept relatively constant near this value during the largest part of the discharging cycle. The heat transfer rate between the HTES and the load varies between 8.5 kW at the initial phase of discharging down to 4.8 kW at the end of the discharging. The outlet temperature of the HTES (RTD5 in in Figure 10) is 45 °C at the start of the discharging and it gradually decreases. At time 0.2 Hours an extreme charging disturbance is manually introduced at the solar circuit that reaches a peak of 38 kW (peak inlet temperature 69 °C and peak flow 25 l/min), in order to observe the response of the discharging controller. Since the charging power is much larger than the discharging power the outlet temperature of the HTES increases to 47.6 °C. During the charging disturbance some small oscillations in the load inlet temperature are observed but the average temperature is successfully maintained at the reference temperature. The oscillations can be due to the flow rate variation during the adjustment of the mixing valve position or due to suboptimal settings of the discharging controller. Nevertheless, these oscillations are not significant and do not affect the performance of the system. After the charging disturbance is stopped, the oscillations are removed and the discharging continues at a relatively constant heat transfer rate of 6 kW. After about 1 Hour the mixing valve is fully open and the load inlet temperature decrease below 40 °C due to the decrease in the PCM temperature. During the whole duration of the test the total thermal energy transferred from the HTES to the load was 9.8 kWh and the total thermal energy transferred from the emulated solar collector to the HTES was 4.8 kWh.

In Figure 11, the temperature at various positions inside the PCM tank is shown. The tank does not discharge uniformly. This is due to high thermal resistance of the PCM material and the effect of local solidification near the heat exchanger fins which further affects the heat transfer rate. Again, the significance of finding the optimal spot for the installation of temperature sensor(s) in the tank is great for the estimation of the average PCM temperature and therefore the state of charge of the tank.

CONCLUSIONS

The control system algorithms for charging and discharging of a HTES PCM tank were tested under laboratory conditions.

- The results validated the correct functionality of the control equipment and the fast and stable performance of the control algorithms with real-time emulation of solar collectors and heating load.
- The emulation platform can successfully emulate the behavior of a real solar collector and thus can be used for the testing of various charging algorithms for solar collectors without the need to install real solar collectors at the testing location.
- Furthermore, because tests involving solar collectors depend on the solar irradiance on the test area and at the time when the test take place, an emulation platform solves that problem by enabling the researcher to simulate the irradiance conditions that they want to test.
- The system build is inexpensive because it only requires a buffer tank with heating elements installed and a controllable mixing valve. The emulation algorithm is fairly simple and can be supported by a wide number of platforms on the market.

The control algorithms will be developed further for the whole system and they will be optimized for the different operating modes and scenarios (e.g. multiple HTES, DHWTES charging/discharging, charging with HP) before they are tested under real operating conditions in the TESSe2b demo sites.

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